

Loan Syndication in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Dr. Abolade Francis AKINTOLA-Department of Finance-Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun-State, Nigeria ⁽²⁾Dr. Samuel Adebayo OLAOYE-Department of Accounting-Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun-State, Nigeria

Abstract

This paper examined loan syndication in Nigeria, focusing on challenges and prospects. The paper highlights parties to loan syndication and the contribution of a syndicated loan to the economic growth of Nigeria as well as the problems and challenges of a syndicated loan. The paper recommends setting up a loan syndication unit in the corporate finance department of banks with well-trained staff in Accounting and Marketing to strengthen the unit for efficient service to the borrowing public.

Keywords: Loan syndication, Economic Growth and Corporate Finance

Introduction

Lending is not a risk-free exercise and there are certain legal and regulatory limitations on lending activities of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Loan syndication has become an attractive credit delivery technique aimed at spreading risk and fine-tuning the credit portfolios of the banks to water down the impact of restricting laws and regulations. An important question to ask is what is loan syndication and how is it done?

Ajibola (2018) stated that a syndicated loan is one granted to a client through the joint participation of three or more financial institutions. Loan syndication can be regarded as an arrangement by which different banks or financial institutions team up to grant a large loan to large scale single borrowers. Such financial institutions come together as a consortium to provide the required facility because the amount required may be too large and risky for a single bank to provide.

Olusemore (2009) defined syndication as an arrangement where a group of banks that may not have any other business relationship with the borrower participate for a single loan. He stated further that it is a lending arrangement in which several or many banks participate. Developments in the Nigerian economy since the introduction of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) on September 26, 1986 have increased the business of loan syndication by Nigeria banks. The drastic depreciation in the external value of the naira in battling inflation and the high cost of importation of equipment by telecommunication companies and companies in the oil industry has further increased the business of loan syndication. According to Olusemore (2009), syndication is familiar with large ticket transactions such as in the oil and gas as well as steel industries. Depending on the size, loan syndication funds could be applied to meet any or all of the following borrowing need: working capital, fixed asset acquisition needs, financing of capital projects as well as a combination of the above.

Adekanye (2010) stated the condition for loan syndication in Nigeria as follows:

- That the loan must be provided by at least three (3) financial institutions
- The loan must be to a single borrower such that the facility will be governed by a single loan agreement
- All the participating lending institutions must be prepared to share the risk involved in a large, medium or long-term loan being packaged to a single borrowing client.

Reasons for Loan Syndication

Onwuaghara (2000) stated some reasons why banks enter into syndication in providing loans for their customers as follows:

- To conform with Banking Act which prescribed the maximum amount that can be lent to a single borrower (single obligor limit).
- To comply with the sectorial allocation of credit, banks could lend through syndication so as to meet the maximum prescribed limit for each sector of the economy particularly the preferred sectors i.e sectorial allocation.

- When banks are facing a liquidity problem, they could embark on syndication to provide loans for viable projects instead of declining requests from a valuable customer.
- Since loans are the most profitable and risky assets, banks would like to protect themselves by sharing the risks through syndication. Sharing the risk will equally reduce the level of bad debt the bank will carry.
- Banks like to be identified with the progress of viable projects. By participating in loan syndication, many banks are associated with the progress and economic growth of corporate bodies and governments.
- Control, management and repayment procedures are better streamlined in a syndicated credit than when the same customer borrows the same amount from different banks on a participating basis.

Parties to Loan Syndication

Dennis and Mullineaux (2000) stated that there are two parties to loan syndication i.e the borrower and the lenders. Olusemore (2009) discussed parties to loan syndication as follows:

Arranger/Lead Bank

The lead bank is the bank that is awarded the mandate by the prospective borrower and is responsible for placing the syndicated loan with other banks and ensures that the syndication is fully subscribed.

Underwriting Bank

This is the bank that agrees to supply the funds to the borrower if necessary from its own resources if the loan is not fully subscribed. However, it should be pointed out that not all syndicated loans are underwriting.

Facility Manager/Agent Bank

This bank takes care of all the administrative arrangements over the term of the loan e.g disbursements, repayments, compliance. The bank acts on behalf of all the banks participating.

Participating Bank

This is a member of the syndication which lends a portion of the total amount required. It is entitled to interest and other participating fees.

Pricing of Syndicated Loan

The arranger and other members of the lead management team generally earn some form of fee in exchange for putting the deal together (Gadanecz, 2004). Syndicated credits are priced according to the perceived credit risk of the borrower. Pricing obviously varies according to the type of borrower, the purpose of loan whether the loan is secured or not and other factors (Casu, Giraidone & Molyneux, 2006).

In Nigeria, like all other bank charges, pricing/charges on loan syndication is governed by the Central Bank of Nigeria tariff that is issued from time to time as presented below:

Table 1: Charges for Consortium Lending

Fee	Type	Remark
Processing	One-off (negotiable)	Collectible upon conclusion of loan documentation
Management fee	Per annum (negotiable)	Lead/agent bank is paid an annual management fee for administration of the loan for its duration
Legal fee	One-off (negotiable)	Incurred by the lead bank paid by the borrower
Participation fee/income	Per annum (negotiable)	Received by all the participating banks
Commitment fee	Per annum charged on undrawn part (negotiable)	Paid as long as the facility is not utilised to compensate the lender for trying up the capital corresponding to the commitment
Agency fee	Per annum (negotiable)	Remuneration of the agent bank's services
Facility fee	Per annum (negotiable)	Payable to banks in return for providing the facility
Underwriting fee	Front-end (negotiable)	Price of the commitment to obtain financing during the first level of syndication
Other fees		Cost of printing, travelling, advertising borne by the borrower

Source: Compiled by Authors from CBN Tariff

Methods of Arranging a Syndicated Loan

Three main methods of arranging for a syndicated loan are

Straight Forward Syndication: This is syndication where the lead bank: structures and packages the facility for the borrower; forms a syndicate of a consortium of lenders to provide the loan.

Club Arrangement: This is a syndicated loan initiated by the borrower usually a corporate body of high credit standing and reputation. The company

- i) Structures and arranges the loan
- ii) Invites banks to participate in the syndicated facility
- iii) Appoints agent bank to co-ordinate the participating banks and assists the lead bank in its marketing effort for the loan

Participating Method: It is the lead bank that packages and arranges the loan; however, it gives the commitment to provide the amount of the loan. It allows for underwriting.

Stages in Loan Syndication

Echekoba and Okonkwo (2015) identified three (3) stages in loan syndication as:

The Contract/Mandate Stage

This is the stage where the basic groundwork and infrastructure for the successful prosecution of the syndication are initiated and laid (Macdonald, 1995). Usually, a prospective loan applicant draws up its credit requirement and the most suitable package that would maximize its expected utility. These catalogues of requirements are presented to a bank or banks that can help in procuring the desired credit.

The Contract Documentation Stage

Amani (2004) stated that this stage gives a legal effect to the syndication of the loan and the various agreement reached. The lead bank arranges the drafting of all the legal documents to bind the parties. All the parties involved must then vet the document before they are executed. The legal instrument specifies the details of the contractual agreement between the lenders and the borrowers. The legal instruments are the loan agreement, the agreement between the lender and the security requirement of the loan.

The Post Signing/Credit Administration: This is the extension by the lead bank of invitation (coupled with the information memorandum) to other financial institutions to participate in the syndication by making provisional commitments up to a given amount and sending in their approval-in-principle before some specified date. On the receipt of favourable responses from other institutions, the lead bank then prepares for the most crucial stage in the syndication process. Glyn (2004) emphasized that the lead bank has the responsibility to liaise closely with the borrower to ensure compliance.

Loan Agreement

This is the document that commits the borrower and syndicate lenders to the terms and conditions of the mandate (Ajibola, 2018). The loan agreement contains the following:

- The desire of the borrower to obtain credit facilities from the lenders as approved by the Board of Directors
- The amount and type of facilities e.g term loans, overdraft, letters of credit etc
- Appointment of lead bank
- The security offered and sharing formula
- The loan amount from each participating bank
- The purpose of the facilities
- Interest chargeable and mode of payment
- Prepayment, replacement and cancellation of facilities
- Financial and non-financial covenants
- Syndicate meetings-quorum, resolutions etc

Contribution of Loan Syndication to the Growth of Nigeria Economy

Loan syndication permits the pooling of financial resources among financial intermediaries for on-lending to investors units thereby enhancing the quality and efficiency of the financial intermediation function.

Loan syndication helps in enhancing investment and the economy's productive capacity by promoting the flow of funds into the industry and other priority sectors of the economy.

Many state governments in Nigeria are also raising large funds to prosecute some of their development projects through loan syndication as in the case of construction of “House for Abuja Civil Servants” where 769 million US dollar was raised through loan syndication. Borno State Ministry of Agriculture. Also through international loan syndication. The country has been able to mobilize required capital for the execution of major economic and social projects. .

Many large corporate bodies that contribute to the economic growth of the nation have been financed through loan syndication few examples are: Nigerian fertilizer company (NAFCON) in Port-Harcourt, Nigerian Paper Mill Limited in Jebba to mention but few.

Through loan syndication, Nigerian banks have continued to support the industrialization policy of the government including economic growth and reduction in the level of unemployment.

Statutory restriction on lending to anyone customer i.e single obligor limit through Banking Act and Central Bank Credit and monetary guidelines make it difficult for a single bank to grant loans of a certain amount to a single customer has been removed through loan syndication.

Through loan syndication, the borrower is saved the pains of raising independently from different financial institutions having to prepare costly separate documentations for each little credit and negotiating one on one the different lender’s terms and conditions.

Table 2: Top-10 Banks in the Nigerian Loan Syndication Market (2006-2010)

Bank	Amount (US\$ m)	No of Deals
Platinum Habib Bank Plc	9,576.23	10
Access Bank Nigeria Plc	8,953.39	9
First Bank of Nigeria Plc	8,808.39	9
Oceanic Bank International Nigeria Plc	7,431.85	9
Stanbic IBTC Bank Plc	8,717.54	9
United Bank for Africa Plc	7,211.00	9
First City Monument Bank Plc	8,688.39	8
Guaranty Trust Bank Plc	8,688.39	8
Standard Chartered Bank Nigeria Plc	8,799.54	8
Zenith Bank Plc	8,684.65	8

Source: First Bank Research

Table 3: Profile of Syndicated Loan in Nigeria

Project Syndicated/Beneficiary	Amount Involved (US\$ Millions)	Banks Involved	Year
Transcorp-Acquisition of 75% stake of NITEL	750.00	A consortium of Nigerian banks	2006
Obajana Cement Plc –Construction	160.00	Consortium of Nigerian banks	2006
Celtel-Network Expansion	1,584.00	12 Nigerian banks and 13 international banks	2007
Zenon Petroleum	1,500.00	BNP Paribas of France & 9 local banks	2007
House for Abuja Civil Servants	769.00	Oceanic bank and two other local banks	2007
Xechem Pharmaceutical	7.69	Bank PHB & Diamond bank	2007
Elеме petrochemicals	123.00	Stanbic bank, UBA and Fidelity bank	2007
AES Nigeria Barge 270MW Power Station Project	25.00	Local banks	2007
MLNG Trains	50.00	Local facility agent	2007
NNPC/MPN NGLII Project Financing	50.00	Nigerian banks	2007
NNPC/MPN \$600m Satellite Oil Field Financing	90.00	Local & international banks	2007
Lekki Infrastructure Project	46.15	Local banks	2007
Refinancing the New Lagos Airport Terminal Project	153.85	Access, First bank, GTB, Oceanic, Zenith, FCMB	2007
MMA2 Lagos Project	250.00	Oceanic bank	2007
MTN Nigeria	2,000.00	A consortium of 21 foreign and Nigerian banks and financial institutions	2007
Econ Mobile-finance exploratory and production activities	265.00	United Bank for Africa Plc, Oceanic bank, Standard Chartered Bank, Skye Bank, Zenith Bank, Bank PHB, Access Bank and Union Bank Plc	2008
Lafage Cement-WAPCO-Ewekoro	268.74	Stanbic-IBTC, GTBank, Std Chartered, First Bank	2009
Expansion Plant		UBN, Ecobank, Bank PHB, Access, FCMB	
Main Street Technologies	120.00	AfDB, DEG, First Bank of Nigeria Plc, Skye Bank	2009

		Plc	
MTN Nigeria	2,150.00	Access Bank, Afribank, Bank PHB, Citibank, Diamond Bank, Ecobank, FCMB, Fidelity Bank, First Bank, GTBank, Stanbic IBTC, Standard Chartered Bank, Union Bank, UBA, Zenith Bank, Industrial & Commercial Bank of China and KfW IPEX-Bank of Germany	2010
Accu Gas Limited	60.00	Stanbic IBTC, UBA	2010
Etisalat-Network expansion	650.00	First Bank, Zenith Bank, Access Bank, Fidelity Bank, Bank PHB, GTBank, UBA, and Oceanic Bank	2011
Shell Petroleum Development Company of Nigeria Limited-Shell Contractor Support Fund	30.00	First Bank, Zenith Bank, UBA	2011

Source: First Bank Research

Deposit money banks still dominate the primary syndicate market all over the world and they appear not in a hurry to leave the space

Challenges of Loan Syndication in Nigeria

Certain problems constrain the syndication of the loan in Nigeria. One of the problems is that bankers are concerned with the relatively long-term nature of syndicated lending and its serious implication for liquidity. Once committed, a syndicated loan implies the trading of liquid resources for medium to long-term illiquidity. Negotiating Pricing: This could be a serious problem where participating banks have to vary cost structures. Another challenge is how to consolidate the multiplicity of charges from participating banks and to get the borrower to accept such charges.

One of the serious challenges is convincing the customer that the lead bank can manage the various relationships and that the interest of the customer will continue to be protected.

The payment of interest and principal when due occasionally poses some problems. The borrower may be facing liquidity problems, low sales turnover, diversion of working capital into acquisition of fixed assets or unprofitable ventures and this may not allow the borrower to meet its obligations to the lenders when due. Such problems if not properly handled, may lead to rescheduling, restructuring and refinancing of the loan.

Conclusion

With the depreciation of naira as a result of structural adjustment programme (SAP) leading to high cost of importation and installation of heavy equipments for use by industries in Nigeria, loan syndication will assist Nigeria companies in achieving their corporate objectives by financing companies in the procurement and installation of these heavy equipments to be used in production of goods and services. This fact can be attested to considering the huge sum of money granted to MTN Nigeria, Celtel-Network expansion, WAPCO to mention but few as can be seen in table 3 of this paper. From the above discussion, it can be concluded that loan syndication has been playing an important role and will continue to play a more important role in Nigeria’s economic growth and development.

Recommendations

The complaint by most borrowers in respect of loan syndication is that the corporate finance department handling this service is not adequately staffed to provide the needed service. This paper recommends that a unit should be set up in the corporate finance department saddled with the responsibility of handling loan syndication.

Similar to the recommendation above is the loan syndication unit should have well-trained staff in Accounting, Marketing that can quickly attend to matters.

One of the complaints is the multiplicity of charges, which have increased the cost of loan syndication, thereby making it unattractive to borrowers.

We recommend a reduction in existing charges and the elimination of some charges to bring down the cost of borrowing on loan syndication.

In addition to the recommendation above, every bank should formulate conscious loan syndication policies and strategies with requisite top management to handle loan syndication businesses.

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